

FUNCTIONALIZED GRAPHENE-BaTiO₃/FERROELECTRIC POLYMER NANOCOMPOSITES WITH EXCELLENT DIELECTRIC PROPERTIES

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Keywords: Graphene; Barium titanate; Nanocomposite; Dielectric properties.

1 Introduction

Over past decades, tremendous researchers have paid their attention to developing dielectric materials with high permittivity (high k) which are very important for the fabrication of high energy density capacitors.[1] Polymers, such as polyethylene (PE), polypropylene (PP), and poly(vinylene fluoride) (PVDF) have long been used as dielectric media for flexible capacitors due to their high electrical breakdown strength, light weight, low cost, and processing flexibility. However, the relatively low dielectric constant (ϵ) severely limits the application of polymers as dielectrics for modern high energy density capacitors. Thus, it is natural to design and fabricate high k composites by using polymers as matrix and species of high dielectric constant as fillers.

Up to now, there are mainly two types of fillers have been widely incorporated within polymers to enhance their dielectric constant.[2] One is ceramic particles with high dielectric constants, and the other

is conductive materials including carbon black (CB), carbon nanotubes (CNTs), graphene, metal nanoparticles, conjugated polymers, etc. Each type of fillers evaluates the dielectric permittivity of polymers through quite different mechanisms. By adding high k ceramics into polymer matrix, the effective ϵ of resultant composites can only be increased to several tens when the volume content of ceramic fillers exceeds 50 %.[3, 4] This will obviously lead to the deterioration of mechanical properties and processability of obtained polymer-based composites. In contrary, the effective ϵ of polymer composites can be dramatically enhanced by adding a small volume fraction of conductive fillers. A large enhancement up to several orders of magnitude in the effective ϵ of polymer composites can be observed near the insulator-conductor percolation.[5-7] Despite the large enhancement in ϵ , the introduction of conductive fillers into polymer matrix can also give rise to the increment of dielectric loss and leakage

current, which severely limits the application of resultant composites as dielectrics for high energy density capacitors. In fact, how to developing high-performance polymer composites with high k and low dielectric loss by using fillers of as low concentration as possible is still a key challenge to meet modern electronic device requirements.

Ternary polymer composites co-filled with conductive and high k inorganic fillers can display improved dielectric properties than those of binary composites filled with either type of fillers. For example, Nan et al. have first proposed and demonstrated a ternary polymer composite, wherein conductive spherical nickel particles and 20 vol% of barium titanate (BT) nanoparticles were incorporated with PVDF, showing a high k of 800 at 100 Hz near the percolation threshold of nickel particles.[8] Conductive fillers with high aspect ratios, such as carbon fibers and CNTs, have long been employed to construct ternary high k polymer composites with low percolation thresholds. For instance, a PVDF-based composite with a high k of 150 at 100 Hz was realized by blending with 1 vol% of multi-walled CNTs and 15 vol% of BT nanoparticles.[9] Recently, graphene has attracted intensive attention for its two-dimensional (2D) structure and superior physical properties including high Young's modulus and fracture strength, high thermal conductivity, high electrical conductivity and mobility of charge carriers.[10-12] Due to the large aspect ratio, 2D graphene nanosheets have been demonstrated as an excellent conductive filler to fabricate percolative polymer-based composites with ultralow percolation thresholds.[13-15] Recently, many efforts have been devoted to the fabrication and dielectric properties of polymer composites filled with graphene,[7,16-19] wherein the 2D nanosheets were obtained through either thermal reduction or chemical reduction from graphene oxide (GO). Very recently, ternary polymer composites co-filled with thermally reduced graphene oxide (TRGO) and high k ceramics have also been reported.[20-22] For instance, Tjong et al. have demonstrated that the TRGO-BT/PVDF

nanocomposites can show a high k of 50 and a low loss factor of 0.072 at 1 kHz.[20] However, to our knowledge, studies about the fabrication and dielectric properties of ternary polymer composites co-filled with chemically functionalized graphene nanosheets and high k ceramic nanoparticles are rare in literatures.

In this work, we report the fabrication and dielectric properties of a novel composite system consisting of poly(vinylidene fluoride), surface-functionalized graphene nanosheets, and BT nanoparticles (fRGO-BT/PVDF). This composite co-filled with conductive graphene nanosheets and high k ceramics shows a high ϵ (65) and a relatively low dielectric loss ($\tan \delta = 0.35$) at a high frequency of 1 MHz.

2 Experiments

2.1 Materials and Characterization

PVDF powder (FR903) with the melt flow rate of 2 g/10 min was purchased from Shanghai 3F New Material Co. Ltd. Graphite powder (GP, Sinopharm Chemical Reagent Co. Ltd.) with the size of 300-400 mesh was sieved out prior to use. The BT nanoparticles were commercial products with the average diameter of 100 nm and used as received without any further treatment. All other chemicals and solvents were obtained as analytical grade products and used without further purification.

Atom force microscopy (AFM) was performed by using Nanoscope-IIIa scanning probe microscope in the tapping mode. The samples for AFM observation were prepared by spin-coating dilute DMF dispersion of RGO and fRGO on pre-cleaned silicon wafer. scanning electron microscopy (SEM) observation was performed on a Hitachi S4700 microscope with an accelerating voltage of 20 kV. The samples were frozen in liquid nitrogen and the resulting freshly fractured surfaces were examined. Dielectric properties of the nanocomposites were measured using an Agilent 4294A impedance analyzer system. Before measurements, electrodes were painted with

silver paste onto both sides of the tablet samples.

2.2 Preparation of polyaniline-functionalized RGO (fRGO) hybrid nanosheets

Graphite oxide was first prepared from natural graphite powder through a modified Hummers method.[23] An emeraldine base form of polyaniline was then synthesized by oxidative coupling of aniline as reported previously.[24]

The emeraldine base of polyaniline was dissolved in N,N-dimethylformamide (DMF) at a concentration of 10 mg/mL by stirring the solution overnight and then was sonicated for 12 h. The solution was then filtrated with filter paper to remove the undissolved polyaniline particles. The resultant solution was left for another 24 h in an ultrasonic bath to ensure the complete dissolution of polyaniline in DMF. Meanwhile, graphite oxide was exfoliated through ultrasonication to form a DMF dispersion of graphene oxide (GO) with a concentration of 1 mg/mL. To prepare fRGO, 50 mL of polyaniline dispersion was mixed with 50 mL of GO dispersion. After 1 mL of hydrazine was successively added in, the mixture was heated at 90 °C for 4 h under vigorous stirring. The mixture was then filtrated with a 0.8 μm nylon membrane, washed excessively with DMF. The obtained fRGO nanosheets were redispersed into DMF through ultrasonication prior to use.

2.2 Fabrication of the fRGO/PVDF and the fRGO-BT/PVDF nanocomposites

The fRGO/PVDF and fRGO-BT/PVDF nanocomposites were fabricated through a two-step approach. Desired amount of fRGO nanosheets and BT nanoparticles were premixed in DMF through ultrasonication to form a stable homogeneous dispersion. The dispersion was then added into a PVDF solution. The mixture was further stirred for 2 h at 80 °C and casted on a precleaned glass plate to form a thin film. After dried at 70 °C for 3 days, the obtained thin films were stacked together and molded by hot-pressing at 200 °C under a pressure of 15 MPa to give tablet samples with the diameter of 12 mm and the thickness of 1 mm.

3 Results and Discussion

To suppress the enhancement in dielectric loss of polymer matrix, fRGO nanosheets with a “core-shell” structure, which were composed of chemically reduced graphene oxide wrapped by insulating polyaniline (leucoemeraldine) through π - π stacking, were selected as the conductive filler. Many literatures have reported that the dielectric properties of polymer composites filled with conductive particles often suffer from high loss factor and high leakage current because of the conduction nature of the fillers.[1] Xu et al. have first demonstrated that by using core-shell particles in which the conductive particles are decorated with insulating shells can efficiently reduce the increment in dielectric loss of polymer composites because of the restriction of insulating layers on electron transfer between conductive particles.[25] Recently, we have found that the surface functionalization of CNTs with insulating polyaniline can not only enhance their compatibility with polymer matrix but also endow the resultant polymer composites with improved dielectric properties.[24] Thus in this work we prepared the polyaniline-functionalized graphene (fRGO) nanosheets with an insulator-conductor-insulator sandwich structure and investigated the structural effect on the dielectric properties of PVDF. The fRGO nanosheets were prepared by reducing exfoliated graphite oxide in the presence of polyaniline.

The as-prepared fRGO nanosheets were carefully characterized by Raman, XPS, and AFM methods. The detail characterization data can be found in a previous paper of our group.[26] The results clearly verified that polyaniline chains have been successfully absorbed onto RGO nanosheets through non-covalent interactions. A typical AFM image of fRGO nanosheets is reappeared as Fig. 1. It can be observed that after functionalization with polyaniline the thickness of RGO nanosheets increased from 1.1 nm to 2.8 nm. According to these thickness values, the weight ratio of RGO to polyaniline in fRGO can

be calculated to be 1.1. This ratio is further used to calculate the volume fraction of fRGO nanosheets in PVDF composites.

To investigate the dielectric properties of ternary fRGO-BT/PVDF nanocomposites, the dielectric properties of binary RGO/PVDF and fRGO/PVDF nanocomposites were firstly examined. Fig. 2a and 2b shows the variations of dielectric permittivity of RGO/PVDF and fRGO/PVDF composite films with the alternating electric field frequency at room temperature, respectively. A common feature that can be seen in both figures is that the addition of RGO or fRGO increases the dielectric permittivity of PVDF host. The promotion in dielectric permittivity can be mainly attributed to a gradual formation of microcapacitor networks in the PVDF matrix as the volume fraction of conductive fillers increases. The microcapacitors consist of RGO or fRGO nanoplatelets separated by a thin insulating PVDF layer. For the composites filled with conductive fillers, the percolation theory depicts that the variations of dielectric constant with frequency follows a power law as the filler content approaches percolation threshold. In our composite system, the power law can be expressed by the following equation:

$$\varepsilon_{\text{eff}} \propto \varepsilon_{\text{PVDF}} (f_c - f)^{-s} \quad \text{for } f < f_c \quad (1)$$

where ε_{eff} represents the dielectric constant of composites, $\varepsilon_{\text{PVDF}}$ is the dielectric constant of PVDF, f is the volume fraction of filler, f_c is the percolation threshold and s is the critical exponent. The numerical fitting of the experimental data according to the equation (1) gives $f_c(\text{RGO}) = 2.45 \text{ vol\%}$ and $f_c(\text{fRGO}) = 1.49 \text{ vol\%}$.

To further understand the effect of the polyaniline shell on the dielectric properties, nanocomposites filled with 1.76 vol% of RGO and 1.40 vol% of fRGO were compared. Both of the filler contents in the samples are close to, but slightly less than, the percolation threshold. As shown in Fig 3, the dielectric permittivity of the samples decreases exponentially with an increase in frequency at low-frequency region (10^2 - 10^5 Hz). When the

frequency is over 10^5 Hz, the dielectric permittivity attains a relatively stable value. The frequency dependence behavior of the dielectric constants in the low-frequency range should be mainly ascribed to the Maxwell-Wagner-Sillars (MWS) polarization. It is noted that the fRGO/PVDF nanocomposite exhibits higher dielectric constants than that of RGO/PVDF at lower frequency region ($< 10^4$ Hz).

For the composites filled with fRGO nanosheets, although a high ε_{eff} of ca. 300 can be achieved near the f_c , the simultaneously increased dielectric loss makes the composites unacceptable for the practice use as dielectric materials. Thus four fRGO/PVDF composites with the f_{fRGO} of 0, 0.63 vol%, 0.94 vol%, 1.25 vol%, wherein the f_{fRGO} is far away from the f_c , were chosen as matrices to fabricate multi-component fRGO-BT/PVDF nanocomposites. The four nanocomposites were denoted as Matrix-1, Matrix-2, Matrix-3, and Matrix-4, respectively.

The dielectric permittivity of fRGO-BT/PVDF nanocomposites with different contents of fRGO and BT over different frequencies at room temperature is shown as Fig. 4. For a given fRGO content, the ε_{eff} of the nanocomposites at a fixed frequency increases with the f_{BT} . Under the same BT loading, the nanocomposite with higher fRGO content clearly exhibits higher ε_{eff} . These observations are reasonable because both conductive fRGO nanosheets and high k BT particles can enhance the permittivity of PVDF. It is worth mentioning that the two types of fillers enhance the permittivity of PVDF through quite different mechanisms. The ε_{eff} of composites filled with high k BT particles can be well explained and predicted by the effective medium theory, while the dielectric properties of composites filled with conductive fRGO nanosheets follow the percolation model. It can also be found that the permittivity of fRGO-BT/PVDF nanocomposites becomes more frequency dependent as the fRGO content increases. For instance, the ε_{eff} of Matrix-2 with 30 vol% loading of BT gradually decreases from 60 to 38 as the frequency increases from 100 Hz to 1 MHz, which is reduced by 36.7 %. In contrast, the ε_{eff} of

Matrix-4 with 30 vol% loading of BT decays from 243 to 65 with a decrease of 73.3 %. As described before, this frequency dependent behavior is related to the interfacial polarization, i.e. MWS polarization. In present work, both fRGO nanosheets and BT nanoparticles in the multi-component nanocomposite can enhance the MWS polarization, but the fRGO nanosheets show a stronger influence on the polarization than that of the BT particles, which should be ascribed to their conductive nature. It is also worth noting that the ϵ_{eff} of Matrix-4 at 1 MHz reaches 65 by blending with 30 vol% of BT along with a relatively low loss factor of 0.35. Compared to other reports filled with CNT, graphene, and high k ceramics,[9,20,22] the fRGO-BT/PVDF nanocomposite in this work exhibits better dielectric properties (high k : 65, low loss: 0.35) at 1 MHz, which is very promising for applications as high-frequency dielectric materials.

4 Conclusions

In this work, a novel ternary PVDF-based nanocomposite system co-filled with fRGO nanosheets and BT nanoparticles was investigated. The fRGO nanosheets were prepared through π - π stacking of polyaniline and GO following in-situ hydrazine reduction. The fRGO-BT/PVDF nanocomposites were fabricated by a solution cast and hot-pressing approach. The dielectric properties of binary fRGO/PVDF nanocomposites exhibit a typical percolation transition with the percolation threshold of 1.49 vol%. Compared with the binary nanocomposites, the fRGO-BT/PVDF nanocomposites show much higher permittivity and lower dielectric loss over the frequency range of 10^2 - 10^6 Hz. At 1 MHz, a high permittivity of 65 and a relatively low loss tangent of 0.35 could be achieved for the fRGO-BT/PVDF nanocomposites. These flexible, high k fRGO-BT/PVDF nanocomposites are potential flexible dielectric materials for high-frequency capacitors and electronic devices.

Acknowledgements

The financial support from the NSFC (51103011, 51073015), the Fundamental Research Funds for the Central Universities (FRF-TP-11-003B), the Ministry of Sciences and Technology of China through China-Europe International Incorporation Project (2010DFA51490), Project of Beijing Municipal Commission of Education (KM201210012010), and State Key Laboratory of Electrical Insulation and Power Equipment (EIPE12207, EIPE12208), is gratefully acknowledged.

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Fig. 2. Dependence of dielectric permittivity of (a) RGO/PVDF films and (b) fRGO/PVDF films with different volume fraction of fillers on the alternating electric field frequency at room temperature.

Fig. 1. Typical AFM images of RGO (left) and fRGO (right) nanosheets on silicon. Reprinted with permission from ref [26], Copyright 2013 RSC Publishing.

Fig. 3. Frequency dependence of dielectric permittivity of RGO/PVDF and fRGO/PVDF nanocomposites with the filler volume fraction near the percolation threshold.

Fig. 4. The frequency dependent dielectric permittivity of (a) BT/PVDF, (b) fRGO-BT/PVDF ($f_{\text{RGO}} = 0.63$ vol%), (c) fRGO-BT/PVDF ($f_{\text{RGO}} = 0.94$ vol%), and (d) fRGO-BT/PVDF ($f_{\text{RGO}} = 1.25$ vol%) with different BT volume fractions measured at room temperature. Reprinted with permission from ref[26]. Copyright 2013 RSC Publishing.